

Effect of Sugar Cane Juice Substrate Formulation and Fermentation Duration on the Quality of Simulated Palm Wine

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ABSTRACT

*Palm wine is obtained from palm sap tapped from oil palm tree (*Elaeise guineenses*) or raffia palm (*Raphia hookeri*) and subsequent spontaneous fermentation by yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*). This study is aimed at determining the effect of sugar cane juice substrate formulation and fermentation period on the quality of simulated palm wine produced using a locally fabricated fermenter, with yeast isolated from palm wine. Sugar cane juice was blended with water at the ratios of 100:0, 70:30 and 50:50 % and subjected to regulated fermentation in the fermenter for 12, 24 and 48 hours respectively. The quality of the simulated palm wine was determined using sensory evaluation and physiochemical analyses. The result showed that samples containing 70:30 % and fermented for 24 hours (H_{24Z} and S_{24T}) had higher ethanol values (8.47 : 7.00%), higher pH (4.34 :4.10), higher sucrose (8.03 :3.65%) and higher total soluble solids (8.35:6.06%) than samples produced from a blend of 100:0 % or 50:50 % and fermented for 12 or 48 hours. Samples H_{24Z} and S_{24T} had values that were not significantly different from those of natural palm wine(P_{24M}) ; ethanol (6.16 %), sucrose (4.17 %) and pH (4.10) respectively. The sensory evaluation result showed that samples H_{24Z} and S_{24T} were the most preferred by the panelist in terms of taste, smell, color, sweetness and their scores were comparable to those of natural palm wine. Conclusively, the quality of the produced simulated palm wine was influenced by the sugar cane juice: water blend ratio and the fermentation period.*

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1.1 INTRODUCTION

There is scarcity of natural palm wine while the demand for palm wine is in the increase (Onuche, 2012; and Ikegwu 2014). The annual demand for palm wine has been reported to be 28.2million litres while the supply is 20% of the annual demand (Mora and Muis 2020). Obtaining good quality palm wine requires climbing the palm tree two or three times a day to tap the sap or to cut down the palm tree. These are entrenched with fatality, injury and loss of palm trees. Up to 18-25% of tappers falling from palm tree have been reported dead (Onuche, 2012).

There is a noticeable dearth of tappers of recent, as the original tappers are getting older the younger men are not showing interest in palm wine tapping as a career (WHO, 2007; Mbuagbaw and Noorduyn, 2012). There is compelling need to fabricate a fermenter that could be suitable for fermentation to produce a beverage with palm wine-like characteristics industrially, with minimal dependence on climbing of palm trees or cutting down palm trees .

1.2 Aim and Objectives of the Research

The study is aimed at producing simulated palm wine from formulated sugar cane juice as an alternative to palm sap and fermenting the juice in the fabricated fermenter using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* isolated from palm wine. This aim could be achieved using the following specific objectives:

- (1) To design and fabricate a basic fermenter for simulated palm wine production
- (2) To extract, process and formulate sugar cane juice into fermentable substrate as palm sap substitute for simulated palm wine production.
- (3) To isolate *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* that will serve as starter culture for simulated palm wine production
- (4) To produce fermented simulated palm wine and to compare its quality with that of natural palm wine.
- (5) To determine the physicochemical and sensory quality of simulated palm win

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Sourcing of Fresh Palm Wine Samples for Isolation of Yeast.

Fresh palm wine samples obtained from oil palm tree species (*Elaeis guineensis*) was sourced from Mowe and Sango in Ogun State, Nigeria. The fresh palm wine samples were purchased from the tappers as they alighted from the palm trees on the arranged days at between 6:30am to 8:00am. The sap were collected in sterile bottles (1500 ml) and placed in ice packed bags and taken to the laboratory for yeast isolation and microbial analysis.

The sourced palm wine samples were stored at room temperature for 12 h, 24 h and 48 h and used as a reference or comparison with produced simulated palm wine samples fermented for 12, 24 and 48 h respectively.

2.2 Description of the designed and fabricated fermenter

The locally fabricated fermenter (Figures 1-3) is made up of three vessels; namely fermentation vessel (FV), which has capacity of 4 L and made of stainless steel with a covering lid. The fermentation vessel is used as the propagation vessel for the yeast and also served as the vessel where initiation of fermentation occurred. The substrate was usually filled into the FV through the feeder funnel (FF). Centrally mounted in the fermentation Vessel (FV) is the triple bladed stainless steel mixer (M) used for the intermittent stirring of the substrate during the propagation and fermentation periods. The fermentation vessel is connected to the immobilization vessel (IV) with stainless steel pipe of 0.01 m diameter. Connected to this pipe are the substrates sampling tap (ST) and a flow control valve (CV₁). The control valve is used to control the flow of the substrate into the immobilization vessel. The sampling tap is used for taking samples for analysis in the course of fermentation process. The immobilization vessel is also made of stainless steel and has capacity of 2 L. The immobilization vessel is stuffed to two-third of its capacity with the loofa-loofa sponge (*Luffa cylindrica*). The loofa sponge has average aperture size of 0.001 m and is made of fibro-vascular reticulated structure with an open network of random lattice of Small cross sections. According to Saeed *et al.*, (2013) loofa-loofa sponge has very high porosity (79-93 %), with very low density 0.02-0.04 g/cm and high specific pore volume 21-29 cm/g and its performance as an immobilization matrix ranks higher than in the conventionally used synthetic polymeric materials for the production of ethanol. The mesh is used to retain, restrain and immobilize most of the yeast within the mesh and to sieve out some of the debris contained in the fermenting substrate as it flows through the immobilization vessel. The immobilization vessel is connected to the retaining vessel (RV) with stainless steel pipe 0.15 M long and 0.01m diameter. The flow through this pipe is regulated with control valve (CV₂) connected to it. The (RV) has 4L capacity and functions as the receiver of the fermented simulated palm wine samples before being dispensed into receiver bottles through the outlet tap (OT) connected to the base of the receiving (RV) vessel. The components of the fermenter are made of stainless-steel pipes, vessels taps, lids and valves as to achieve sanitary conditions required for fermenter design conditions as recommended by Gaikward *et al.*, (2018) for fermenter components to prevent rusting and other reactions. These vessels and their piping arrangements were all mounted on the carrier iron stand (IS) and connected to ensure the continuous flow of substrate under gravitational force at a gradient of 1.3:1.2:1.0 (FV: IV: RV).

Figure 2.1: Engineering drawing of the locally fabricated fermenter

PART LIST

ITEM	QTY	PART NUMBER	MATERIAL
1.	1	Fermentation Vessel Cover	Stainless Steel FVV
2	1	Feeder Funnel	Stainless Steel FF
3	1	Frame	Mild, Steel FM
4	1	Fermentation Vessel	Stainless Steel FV
5	1	Mixer	Stainless Steel MX
6	1	Funnel Cover	Stainless Steel CF
7	2	Vessel Cover	Stainless Steel VC
8	1	Retaining Vessel	Stainless Steel RV
9	1	Immobilization Vessel	Stainless Steel IM
10	1	Control Valve	Generic CY
11	1	Tap	Stainless Steel TP
12	1	Pipes	Stainless Steel PP

Figure 2.2: Exploded drawing of the components of the fermenter

Figure 2.3: 3D design of the fermenter

2.3 Sugar cane Juice Extraction and Formulation for simulated palm wine production

Freshly harvested sugarcane stalk (*Saccharum officinarum*) of the purple-red variety was purchased from Idi-oro market, Mushin Lagos State. The sugar cane juice was extracted following the modified procedure of Geremias-Andrades, (2014). The process involved washing the canes with sterile water, then sorting the stems; after which they were peeled with sharp stainless-steel knives. The canes were cut and their juice expressed out using the sugar cane juice extractor (Model: Omega NC800HDS). The extracted juice was pasteurized at 70 °C for 10mins and allowed to cool to room temperature (25 ± 2 °C) after which, the juice was filtered to remove sediments in the juice.

The sterilized sugarcane juice was blended with sterilized water at the ratio of 50% sugar cane juice to 50% water (50:50) FOF; 70% sugar cane juice to 30% water SOT (70:30) and 100% sugar cane juice to 0% water HOZ (100:0). These blend ratios were formulated respectively as substrate for producing the simulated palm wine

Figure 2.4: Extraction of sugar cane juice and Formulation of substrate for simulated palm wine production

2.4 Microbial Analysis

2.4.1 Identification, characterization and isolation of palm wine yeast

Pure *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was isolated from fresh palm wine sourced from Mowe (P₁₂M) and Sango (P₁₂S). The yeast was identified using serial dilution and morphological characterization as described by Ben David et al., (2014); Allen (2013) and Onwuamah et al., (2019). The isolated *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* were further confirmed using molecular characterization procedure of Ebabhi (2013) and as elaborated using DNA extraction protocol, PCR-amplification and sequencing procedures (Zymo Research purification procedure, 2012)

2.4.2 Propagation of Isolated *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

Pure *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* colony was obtained from the pure culture plate and dispensed in 10ml sterile water contained in 10ml sterile tube. The quantity of cells dispensed was sufficient to create a turbidity equivalent to 2% McFarland standard solution turbidity. 2% McFarland solution turbidity is equivalent to 4.0×10^4 CFU/ml. Twenty (20) ml of the suspended yeast cells (equivalent of 4.0×10^8 cfu/ml) was dispensed in one (1) L sterile sugarcane juice and placed in water bath shaker at 28 ± 2 °C (Clifford digital water-bath shaker, UK). The yeast was allowed to grow aerobically under constant agitation for 24 h. This enabled the yeast to grow and build up actively to be used as the starter culture for the simulated palm wine production.

2.5 Fermentation of simulated palm wine using the locally fabricated fermenter

The locally fabricated fermenter was first sanitized by washing it thoroughly with water containing detergent; after which, it was cleaned up with 98% (v/v) ethanol, before it was finally flushed with boiled water. After the sanitization operation, 3 L respectively of the formulated sterilized sugar cane juice substrate sterilized sugar cane juice substrate was poured into the fermentation vessel followed by inoculating one 1 L of the propagated vigorously growing *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* into the vessel and these were mixed very well and subjected to a regulated fermentation period. The fermentation period was split into three periods; namely, the 12 h, 24 and the 48 h fermentation period for each of the blend ratios of 100:0 %, 70:30 % and 50:50 % respectively.

The fermentation process involved allowing the substrate to flow at predetermined velocities from the FV into IV and then into the RV respectively. For the 12 h fermented simulated palm wine, the flow rate was regulated to allow the fermenting substrate to flow from the fermentation vessel (FV) into the immobilization vessel (IV) at the predetermined rate of 0.33 (L/h) and from the (IV) into the retainer vessel (RV) at the rate of 0.17 (L/h) over a period of 12 h and this sample were designated as 12 h fermented simulated palm wine samples (F₁₂F, S₁₂T and H₁₂Z) respectively. For the 24h fermented simulated palm wine, the substrate was made to flow from the fermentation vessel (FV) at the rate of 0.17 (L/h) into the immobilization vessel (IV) and from the IV into the retainer vessel (RV) at the rate of 0.08 (L/h) over a period of 24 h. The samples collected were designated as samples F₂₄F, S₂₄T and H₂₄Z respectively. For the 48 h fermented simulated palm wine samples, the substrate were made to flow from the fermentation vessel (FV) into the immobilization vessel IV at the rate of 0.083 (L/h) and from the (IV) into the retainer vessel (RV) at the rate of 0.043 (L/h) over a period of 48 h. The samples collected from the RV were designated samples F₄₈F, S₄₈T and H₄₈Z respectively.

Each set of fermented simulated palm wine samples were filtered and filled into 350 cm³ bottles, they were corked, pasteurized at 70°C for 10 min and cooled to 25 °C and kept for further use in the refrigerator at 5 ± 2 °C. The quality of the samples produced (F₁₂F, S₁₂T, H₁₂Z, F₂₄F, S₂₄T, H₂₄Z, F₄₈F, S₄₈T, and H₄₈Z; P₁₂M, P₂₄M and P₄₈M) were determined by carrying out physiochemical studies and sensory evaluation on the samples.

The parameters determined included: Total soluble solids, total sugar, ethanol, total acidity, pH, Invert sugar, ash and protein content. These were determined using the AOAC (2019) methods of analysis.

2.6 Physiochemical Analysis of the Samples

The physiochemical compositions of the natural palm wine, sugar cane juice substrate and the produced simulated palm wine were determined using the AOAC (2019) method of analysis. The parameter analyzed included the total soluble solids, sucrose, invert sugar and ethanol content, total ash, crude fat, crude protein, vitamin C, pH and total acidity.

2.7 Sensory Evaluation of the Produced Simulated Palm Wine Samples

The samples produced (F₁₂F, S₁₂T, H₁₂Z, F₂₄F, S₂₄T, H₂₄Z, F₄₈F, S₄₈T) and samples from natural palm wine (P₁₂M, P₂₄M, P₄₈M) were presented to a 40 member sensory panelist selected from ladies and gentlemen above 18 years of age who are used to drinking palm wine and could distinguish sensory attributes of palm wine. These panelists were further trained on the quality characteristics of good palm wine.

They were instructed to evaluate the sensory characteristics of the samples based on their colour, taste, palm wine smell, sweetness and overall acceptability, using a 9-point hedonic scale that ranged from 9-like extremely, 8-like very much, 7-like moderately, 6-like slightly, 5-neither like nor dislike; 4-dislike slightly, 3-dislike moderately, 2-dislike very much and 1-dislike extremely. They were asked to express their perception of the samples presented and score the parameters on their resemblance to natural palm wine samples using the accompanying questionnaire.

2.8 Statistical Analysis

Data obtained from physiochemical and sensory analysis were collated, means were determined and the level of differences between means were statistically analyzed for significant effect on the analyzed parameters at 5% level of significance using analysis of variance (ANOVA) of SPSS version 2.1 as described in the method of Akinjayeju (2017).

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fermenter Design and Fabrication

The locally fabricated fermenter (figure 2.1 – 2.6) was designed to create a bioreactor environment conducive for yeast fermentation in order to produce an acceptable simulated palm wine. The variation in the volume capacities of the vessels was to ensure continuous flow of substrate from the fermentation vessel (FV) to the immobilization vessel (IV) and from the immobilization vessel (IV) to the retainer vessel (RV) under a batch fermentation process. This

process ensured that sugars in the substrate are in real time contact with the yeast, thereby facilitating fermentation. According to Saheed and Igbal (2013) the continuous real time contact of sugar with yeast enhanced the rate of fermentation rate and alcohol yield. This is further enhanced by ensuring that at all times during the fermentation period the substrates flowed from the FV into the IV and then into the RV. The continuous contact of the substrate with the yeast is engineered into the design by incorporation of the loofa sponge in the (IV) and by making the FV to have the same volume with the retainer vessel (RV). The volume of the FV and RV were made equal (4L) to ensure that even as the samples dripped into the retainer vessel, fermentation will still be going on until the whole fermenting batch volume discharges completely into the retainer vessel.

The flow regime across the vessels during the various fermentation periods was continuous all through the respective 12, 24 and 48 h fermentation period. This created a non – stagnant flow situation, thereby bringing about intimate contact between the yeast and the sugar in the substrate, with resultant increase in alcohol yield and diminished product inhibition. According to (Saheed and Igbal, (2013) and Gaikward *et al.*, (2018) the longer the contact time between substrate and the yeast the higher the rate of fermentation and the higher the alcohol yield.

The regulated slow flow rate ($0.048 - 0.17 \text{ L/h}$) achieved in the design of the locally fabricated fermenter is akin to the drip-drop pattern of palm sap as it oozes out from the cut base of the inflorescent flower during the taping of the palm sap and this is consistent with the description of the flow pattern of palm sap during the taping of palm sap (Onuche *et al.*, 2012 and Ikeagwu *et al* 2014).

The effectiveness of the locally fabricated fermenter was further enhanced by the in-built Loofa sponge in the immobilization vessel. The sponge had mesh aperture size of between $0.0048 - 0.0062 \text{ m}$ that could trap, retain and delay the rate of yeast cell escape and flow rate. As the substrate flowed through the sponge matrix, it experienced slow flow rate and longer contact time, larger surface area, increased fermentation rate and higher alcohol yield in the product. This is consistent with the report of Saheed *et al.*, (2013) that loofa sponge acts as immobilizer of yeast cells in bioreactors to enhance the rate of fermentation and alcohol yield.

Table 3.1:

Design parameters and results obtained from the locally fabricated	fermenter		
Parameters	FV	IV	RV
Height (m)	0.154	0.075	0.154
Radius (m)	0.091	0.091	0.091
Volume ($\pi r^2 h$) (m ³)	4	2	4
Flow rate during 12 h fermentation (L/hr)	0.33	0.17	
Flow rate during 24 h fermentation (L/hr)	0.17	0.08	
Flow rate during 48 h fermentation (L/hr)	0.083	0.043	
Distance between FV – IV (m)		0.3	
Distance between IV – RV (m)			0.15
Distance between FV – RV (m)			0.45
Fermenter elevation (m)	0.80	0.80	0.67
Gradient ratio	1.3	1.2	1.0
Fermentation Temperature °C	25-28 °C	25-28 °C	25-28 °C

FV: Fermentation vessel

IV: Immobilization vessel

RV: Retainer vessel

3.2 Physiochemical Composition of Extracted and Formulated Sugar Cane Juice Substrate

The sugar cane variety *Saccharum officinarum*, was particularly used for the research because of its high yield of sugar cane juice (35% - 46% ^v/wt) and its high content of sucrose (9.03% - 12.5%), other sugars and minerals useful for fermentation. Table 3.2 showed that the concentration of sucrose obtained was in the range of 9.01 – 9.02% which compared well with the yield of 10 – 12% sucrose reported by Arif *et al.*, (2019).

The pasteurization of the juice of 70°C for 10 mins was necessary in order to denature enzymes that could cause enzymatic browning reactions. The pasteurization of the sugar cane juice also helped to destroy microorganism that causes diseases and that could be antagonistic to yeast during fermentation (Kunitak *et al.*, 2014). It also contributed to the denaturation of suspended organic matters contained in the sugar cane juice. The pasteurization of the juice not only kills microorganism but also helps produce a more clear coloured sugar cane juice as according to Geremias –Andrades *et al.*, (2014) the denatured organic materials clog together on cooling and are easily filtered off leaving behind a clearer juice suitable for fermentation operation.

The dilution of the pasteurized sugar cane juice with water was in order to formulate three blends of the substrate (100:0 %, 70:30% and 50:50 %) water there by formulating three levels of substrate concentration that may be suitable for yeasts growth and fermentation and may lead to production of different qualities of simulated palm wine. This is corroborated by Barnett *et al.*, (2016) that the dilution of sugar cane juice with water not only reduces the osmotic effect of high

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sugar concentration on yeast cells but may improve higher ethanol yield. The addition of water caused a dilution effect by lowering the sugar concentration in the 100% sugar cane juice from (9.03 %) to 5.15 % (SOT) and 4.46 % (FOF) respectively. However, these values were within the compositional range reported for palm sap by Karamako *et al.*(2016), which ranged from 2.5 – 9.5% for sucrose. The specific gravity (1.03 – 1.01), total soluble solid (9.7 – 4.46), pH (4.46 – 9.7 %) (Table 4.2) obtained in the sugar cane juice substrate formulation were also comparable to those reported as being contained in palm sap; specific gravity (1.013 – 1.025), TSS (6.89 – 9.8 %) and pH (4.45 – 4.87) (Djeni *et al.*, 2020).

These compositional variations occasioned by the dilution effect of water were to subject the yeast to various levels of sucrose, pH and other solids concentration in the different substrate samples in order to produce different variations in the quality of simulated palm wine that could be comparable to natural palm sap, from which an acceptable simulated palm wine samples could be selected based on their physiochemical analysis and sensory evaluation. This variation in the expected quality of the simulated palm wine could create variety in the samples and create different preference levels to the consumers. According to Santiago-Urbina and Ruiz-Terran, (2014) Ikegwu (2014) that palm wine quality varied depending on the source of palm sap, type of palm tree, stage of tapping, season of the year and method of tapping.

The pH (4.85 – 5.23) and total acidity (0.36 – 0.39) of sugar cane juice substrate were not significantly different amongst the samples blends and were also comparable to those reported for palm sap (pH 3.6 – 5.23) (TTA 0.1 – 0.3%) Ibegbulam *et al.*, (2007) These pH and TTA ranges were also reported to be suitable for optimum yeast activity Ghosh *et al.*, (2012). Table 3.3 further showed that the proximate composition of the formulated sugar cane juice substrate contained proteins (0.27 – 0.33%), fat (0.22 – 0.32%) Ash (0.16 – 0.20%), and vitamin C 40.05 – 40.70 mg/100ml that were comparable to those contained in the natural palm sap (Endo *et al.*, (2014) and Lucky *et al.*, 2014). The presence of these nutrients in the substrate at levels comparable to those in the natural palm sap showed that the formulated substrate could support the growth of yeast and could support yeast ability to ferment the sugars to alcohol. It is therefore most probable that an acceptable simulated palm wine could be produced using formulated sugar cane juice substrate and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

Table 3.2 Extraction and formulation of Sugar cane juice parameter

Parameter	Results
Mean juice yield	25 % - 46 %
Sucrose content	9-12 %
Pasteurization Temperature	70 °C for 10 mins
Storage temperature	5± 2 °C
Sugar cane juice:	water blend ratio
100 % sugar cane juice:	0 % water (HOZ)
70 % sugar cane juice:	30 % water (SOT)
50 % sugar cane juice:	50 % water (FOF)

Table 3.3: Physicochemical composition of formulated Sugar cane juice substrate

Means of sample with same alphabet superscripts on a row are not significantly different ($P \leq$

Sample	(HOZ)	(SOT)	(FOF)	F – Statistics (p)
TSS (%)	9.70± 0.14 ^a	7.19 ± 0.04 ^b	6.93 ± 0.05 ^b	594.66 (<0.001)
Sucrose (%)	9.03 ± 0.01 ^a	5.15 ± 0.04 ^b	4.46 ± 0.50 ^b	143.547 (0.001)
Invert sugar (%)	8.35 ± 0.07 ^a	4.80± 0.02 ^b	4.10± 0.16 ^c	979.092 (<0.001)
pH	5.23 ± 0.04 ^a	4.91 ± 0.15 ^a	4.85 ± 0.07 ^a	8.694 (0.056)
Total Acidity as Lactic acid (%)	0.36 ± 0.001 ^a	0.37 ± 0.01 ^a	0.39 ± 0.02 ^a	24.039 (0.014)
Vitamin C (mg/100ml)	49.05 ± 0.07 ^a	41.90± 0.28 ^b	40.70± 0.71 ^b	209.034 (0.001)
Specific gravity	1.03 ± 0.002 ^a	1.02 ± 0.001 ^b	1.01 ± 0.001 ^b	34.357 (0.009)
Glucose (%)	3.63 ± 0.05 ^a	2.71 ± 0.14 ^b	2.47 ± 0.07 ^b	81.197 (0.002)
Protein (%)	0.33 ± 0.01 ^a	0.31 ± 0.03 ^a	0.27 ± 0.01 ^a	6.333 (0.084)
Fat (%)	0.32 ± 0.01 ^a	0.30± 0. ^{01a}	0.22 ± 0.01 ^b	112.000 (0.002)
Ash (%)	0.16 ± 0.03 ^a	0.20± 0.02 ^a	0.20± 0.02 ^a	1.441 (0.364)
Sodium	3.58 ± 0.01 ^a	3.77 ± 0.08 ^a	3.75 ± 0.07 ^a	6.032 (0.089)

0.05)

HOZ: 100% Sugar cane juice with zero fermentation

SOT: 70% Sugar cane juice 30% water, with zero fermentation

FOF: 50% Sugar cane juice 50% water with zero fermentation

3.3 Isolation and Characterization of Yeast Used For the Simulated Palm Wine Fermentation

The results obtained for the microbial population count from the sourced palm wine samples (Table 3.4) showed that all samples contained high population of yeast and lactic acid bacteria. The total lactic acid bacteria count ranged from 4.8×10^2 cfu/ml to 5.2×10^3 CFU/ml, while the total yeast count ranged from 4.3×10^4 CFU/ml to 8.0×10^6 CFU/ml.

The morphological characteristics of the yeast obtained from palm wine sourced from Mowe P₁₂M and Sango P₁₂S (Table 3.5) had morphological characteristics had oval shape; smooth texture, mucoid consistency, raised elevation and entire margin. The yeast was also gram positive and catalase positive. The result of the sugar fermentation test showed that the yeast could ferment sucrose, glucose, Lactose and maltose confirming them to be *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

Generally, the ability of yeast isolated from palm wine sourced from Mowe (P₁₂M) and palm wine from Sango (P₁₂S) (Table 3.6) to ferment, sucrose, glucose and lactose confirms the capacity of the yeast to ferment sugar and they may be very suitable for the production of simulated palm wine. According Ojo-Omoniyi (2020), *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* is mostly responsible for the fermentation of sugar in palm sap to alcohol. This also confirms their ability to utilize sugars and convert them to alcohol. This is consistent with the report of Ebabhi *et al.*, (2013) and Ngoc *et al.*, (2014) that *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* can utilize the carbon sources mostly from hexose sugars.

Table 3.4 Total microbial cell count of palm wine samples from different sources

Samples	Total Lactic Acid Bacteria Count TLABC (Cfu/ml)	Total Yeast and Mold Count TMYC (Cfu/ml)
P ₁₂ M	4.0×10^2	8.0×10^6
P ₁₂ S	3.4×10^3	7.25×10^5

Table 3.5: Morphological characterization of yeast isolates from palm wine samples from different sources

Palm wine Source	Consistency	Shape	Texture	Margin	Elevation	Gram test	Catalase Test	Colour
P ₁₂ M	Mycoïd	Oval	Smooth/moist	Entire	Raised	+	+	Creamy white
P ₁₂ S	Mycoïd	Oval	Smooth/moist	Entire	Raised	+	+	Creamy

Table 3.6: Sugar Fermentation characterization of yeast isolates from palm wine samples

	Xylose	Dextrose	Sucrose	Glucose	Lactose	Galactose	Maltose
P ₁₂ M	-	-	+	+	+	+	-
P ₁₂ S	-	-	+	+	+	+	-

P₁₂M: palm wine from Mowes

P₁₂S: palm wine from sang

3.4 Effect of Fermentation Duration on Physiochemical Characteristics of the Simulated Palm Wine.

The physiochemical composition of simulated palm wine samples (Table 3.8 – 3.10) showed that during the 12 – 48 h fermentation period, there was observed decrease in the total soluble solid, total invert sugar, sucrose contents and specific gravity values of the samples with increasing fermentation period. The decrease of the fermentable sugars with fermentation duration gave a corresponding increase in alcohol production, hence the noticeable differences in percentage alcohol content of different samples (3.49 – 3.31% v/v) for 12 h fermented samples and (3.50 – 8.47% v/v) for 24 h fermented samples and (4.46 – 7.20% v/v) for the 48 h fermented samples. This increase in alcohol content may be as the result of fermentation of the sugar by yeast to produce alcohol and carbon dioxide. This is corroborated by works of Ejimofor *et al.*, (2023) where they obtained similar ethanol values ranging from 5.7-9.44 % (v/v)

This is also consistent with the report of Karamoko *et al.*, (2016) that 50% of sugars in palm sap are fermented to alcohol within few hours of tapping of the palm sap. The result showed that the alcohol content obtained after 12 h to 24 h fermentation of the sugar cane juice substrate (7.00 – 8.47%) were comparable to those obtained from 12 h old natural palm wine obtained from different sources; P₂₄M (6.16) P₂₄S (6.95). This is consistent with the result reported by Endo *et al.*, 2014 and Opara *et al.*, (2013) for alcohol content of 24 h fermented palm wine (7.10 % v/v). The alcohol content of samples H₂₄Z (8.47 %) was higher than that of samples S₂₄T (7.00 %) and F₂₄F (3.3%). The alcohol content of H₂₄Z (8.47 %) and S₂₄T (7.00) were higher and significantly different from those obtained from natural palm wine samples P₂₄S (6.95 %) and P₂₄M (6.16 %). This could confirm the possibility of producing simulated palm wine from sugar cane juice diluted with 30 % water. Diluting the sugar cane juice with 50 % water with consequent

reduction in sucrose concentration may have caused the low yield of alcohol (3.31 – 4.6 % v/v) in the simulated palm wine samples.

Fermentation of the sugar cane juice substrates for 48 h produced simulated palm wine samples that had lower alcohol content 7.20 % (H_{48Z}), 6.35 % (S_{48T}) 4.46 % (F_{48F}) than samples fermented for 24 h, H_{24Z} (8.47%), (7.00%) and F_{24F} (3.50%). These results may have arisen from the possibility of lowering the activity of yeast due to the inhibitory effect of high alcohol concentration and additional oxidation of the alcohol to acetic acid. This may have resulted in the lowering the fermentation ability of yeast under these conditions. This is in tandem with the findings of Ubong and Godwin, (2017) and Opara *et al.*, (2013) that alcohol can be oxidized to acetic acid and the combined inhibitory effect of high acid and alcohol concentration may affect the metabolic activity of yeast.

The pH of the simulated palm wine samples varied very slightly from its initial high level of 4.45 – 4.91 for the 12 h fermented samples to 4.60 – 3.95 for the 48 h fermented simulated palm wine samples. As sugars in the substrate were fermented acids were also produced and the pH lowered. This may have resulted in the high values of pH of 12 h fermented simulated palm wine 4.45 (H_{12Z}), 4.45 (S_{12T}) and 4.49 (F_{12F}); and the lower values of the 48 h fermented simulated palm wine samples H_{48Z} (4.35), S_{48T} (4.15) and F_{48F} (4.46). Generally, the pH of the simulated palm wine samples was comparable to the pH of natural palm wine (pH 4.3 -5.0) as reported by Ukwuru and Awah (2013). These values were consistent with the pH values obtained from palm wine sourced from Mowe P_{12M} (4.05) and palm wine sourced from Sango P_{12S} (4.10).

The acidity of the simulated palm wine which varied from the 12 h fermented simulated palm wine (0.30 – 0.37%) increased to (0.37 – 0.47%) for the 24 hr fermented simulated palm wine samples and to 0.40 – 0.50 for the 48 hr fermented simulated palm wine. The total acidity obtained for the fermented simulated palm wine samples (0.30 – 0.50%) were comparable to the TTA obtained by Karamako *et al.*, (2016) for natural palm wine (0.17 – 0.88%). This further showed that the acidity of the simulated palm wine were within the range acceptable for palm wine. Generally, as the acidity of the simulated palm wine increased, its pH decreased and the level of souring of the palm wine increased.

Table 3.8: Physiochemical Composition of Simulated Palm Wine and Natural Palm Wine after 12 hours fermentation

Parameters	H ₁₂ Z	S ₁₂ T	F ₁₂ F	P ₁₂ M	P ₁₂ S	F(p)
Total soluble solids (TSS %)	8.60 ± 0.73 ^a	6.19 ± 0.04 ^{ab}	5.93 ± 0.5 ^c	7.04 ± 0.20 ^b	5.70 ± 0.14 ^c	20.339 (0.003)
Sucrose %	8.80 ± 0.14 ^a	4.11 ± 0.02 ^d	4.09 ± 0.02 ^d	6.30 ± 0.28 ^b	5.70 ± 0.14 ^c	311.709 (<0.001)
Total sugar (as % invert)	8.35 ± 0.07 ^a	5.70 ± 0.00 ^b	3.75 ± 0.07 ^c	5.10 ± 28 ^c	5.70 ± 0.14 ^b	254.159(<0.001)
Glucose %	2.63 ± 0.05 ^a	2.71 ± 0.14 ^a	2.56 ± 0.01 ⁺	2.70 ± 0.14 ^a	1.95 ± 0.21 ^b	97.017 (< 0.001)
Specific gravity (SPG)	1.053 ± 0.00 ^a	1.036 ± 0.01 ^b	1.035 ± 0.01 ^b	1.020 ± 0.00 ^c	1.038 ± 0.00 ^b	13.695 (0.007)
Ethanol (% vv)	3.49 ± 0.10 ^{ab}	3.50 ± 0.04 ^{ab}	3.31 ± 0.01 ^b	3.57 ± 0.21 ^{ab}	3.74 ± 0.16 ^a	2.999 (0.130)
Ph	4.45 ± 0.07 ^b	4.45 ± 0.07 ^b	4.71 ± 0.15 ^a	4.05 ± 0.07 ^c	4.10 ± 0.14 ^c	20.689 (0.003)
Total Acidity (as Lactic) %	0.30 ± 0.01 ^b	0.37 ± 0.01 ^b	0.30 ± 0.2 ^b	0.69 ± 0.03 ^a	0.60 ± 0.14 ^c	15.360 (0.005)
Fat content (%)	0.22 ± 0.01 ^c	0.42 ± 0.01 ^b	0.22 ± 0.01 ^c	0.61 ± 0.04 ^a	0.33 ± 0.08 ^b	30.791 (0.001)
Protein (%)	0.33 ± 0.01 ^c	0.32 ± 0.04 ^a	0.37 ± 0.02 ^a	0.29 ± 0.01 ^a	0.19 ± 0.20 ^a	1.064 (0.451)
Total ash (%)	0.23 ± 0.02 ^b	0.20 ± 0.02 ^b	0.24 ± 0.01 ^b	0.30 ± 0.01 ^a	0.37 ± 0.08 ^a	5.890 (0.039)
Sodium (mg/100ml)	2.53 ± 0.064 ^d	3.77 ± 0.08 ^c	3.75 ± 0.07 ^c	27.10 ± 0.28 ^a	23.43 ± 0.21 ^b	10425.469 (<0.001)
Vitamin C (mg/100ml)	41.25 ± 0.78 ^a	41.30 ± 0.57 ^a	42.00 ± 0.14 ^a	8.95 ± 0.07 ^c	18.10 ± 0.99 ^b	1272.608 (<0.001)
Sodium chloride (%) 2.20 ± 0.14b	0.016 ± 0.01 ^b	0.018 ± 0.00 ^b	0.020 ± 0.00 ^b	0.075 ± 0.01 ^a	0.065 ± 0.01 ^a	50.544 (<0.001)
Sulphur dioxide (mg/kg)	2.00 ± 0.02 ^b	1.70 ± 0.72 ^b	2.20 ± 0.14 ^b	1.55 ± 0.07 ^b	3.25 ± 0.07 ^a	8.165 (0.020)

Sample of means with same alphabet superscripts on a row are not significantly different (P ≤ 0.05)

Legend:

H₁₂Z: 100% sugar cane juice; 0% added water, substrate fermented for 12 h

S₁₂T: 70% sugar cane juice; water substrate fermented for 12 h

F₁₂F: 50% sugar cane juice; 50% added substrate fermented for 12 h

P₁₂M: Fresh palm wine sourced from Mowe analyzed after 12 h

P₁₂S: Fresh palm wine sourced from Sango analyzed after 12 h

Table 3.9: Physiochemical properties of Simulated palm wine juice and natural palm wine sample after 24 h fermentation

Parameters	H _{24Z}	S _{24T}	F _{24F}	P _{24M}	P _{24S}	F(p)	
Total soluble solids (TSS %)	8.35 ± 0.07 ^a	6.06 ± 0.07 ^a	4.71 ± 0.01 ^c	4.23 ± 0.21 ^c	4.10 ± 0.24 ^d	341.333 (<0.001)	
Sucrose %	8.03 ± 0.01 ^a	3.65 ± 0.07 ^a	3.36 ± 0.01 ^b	4.17 ± 0.30 ^c	2.21 ± 0.16 ^a	601.671 (<0.001)	
Total sugar (as % invert)	8.35 ± 0.07 ^a	5.70 ± 0.00 ^b	3.75 ± 0.07 ^c	1.17 ± 0.21 ^a	1.63 ± 0.17 ^d	1056.945 (<0.001)	
Glucose %	1.67 ± 0.01 ^b	0.11 ± 0.00 ^d	1.50 ± 0.01 ^b	2.50 ± 0.14 ^a	0.75 ± 0.07 ^c	331.650 (< 0.001)	
Specific gravity (SPG)	1.03 ± 0.00 ^a	1.01 ± 0.01 ^a	1.01 ± 0.01 ^a	1.01 ± 0.02 ^a	0.01 ± 0.02 ^a	1.453 (0.341)	
Ethanol (% vv)	8.47 ± 0.08 ^a	7.00 ± 0.14 ^b	3.50 ± 0.01 ^d	6.16 ± 0.08 ^c	6.95 ± 0.21 ^b	426.807 (<0.001)	
pH	4.34 ± 0.02 ^b	4.10 ± 0.00 ^b	4.70 ± 0.07 ^a	4.10 ± 0.14 ^b	4.10 ± 0.14 ^c	17.661 (0.004)	
Total Acidity (as Lactic) %	0.39 ± 0.001 ^c	0.37 ± 0.01 ^c	0.50 ± 0.01 ^c	0.77 ± 0.17 ^a	0.61 ± 0.01 ^{ab}	9.540 (0.015)	
Fat content (%)	0.12 ± 0.00 ^b	0.06 ± 0.01 ^b	0.37 ± 0.02 ^c	0.29 ± 0.01 ^a	0.33 ± 0.08 ^b	26.025 (0.002)	
Protein (%)	0.45 ± 0.01 ^a	0.37 ± 0.02 ^{ab}	0.45 ± 0.01 ^a	0.30 ± 0.3 ^b	0.32 ± 0.07 ^b	7.412 (0.025)	
Total ash (%)	0.16 ± 0.03 ^b	0.13 ± 0.03 ^c	0.22 ± 0.02 ^b	0.29 ± 0.01 ^a	0.32 ± 0.07 ^b	27.859 (0.001)	
Sodium (mg/100ml)	3.62 ± 0.12 ^d	6.46 ± 0.32 ^b	4.20 ± 0.14 ^c	22.99 ± 0.01 ^a	23.43 ± 0.21 ^a	5806.940 (<0.001)	
Vitamin C (mg/100ml)	49.05 ± 0.07 ^a	40.90 ± 0.57 ^c	44.10 ± 0.14 ^b	8.97 ± 0.17 ^d	8.97 ± 0.30 ^d	8464.569 (<0.001)	
Sodium chloride (%)	2.20 ± 0.14 ^b	0.018 ± 0.02 ^a	0.016 ± 0.001 ^c	0.017 ± 0.001 ^c	0.045 ± 0.01 ^b	0.065 ± 0.01 ^{ab}	19.620 (<0.003)
Sulphur dioxide (mg/kg)	2.11 ± 0.01 ^b	1.27 ± 0.92 ^d	1.50 ± 0.15 ^{cd}	1.60 ± 0.14 ^c	3.15 ± 0.07 ^a	118.499 (<0.001)	

Sample of means with same alphabet superscripts on a row are not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$)

Legend:

H_{24Z}: 100 % sugar cane juice; 0% added water, substrate fermented for 24 h; S_{24T}: 70% sugar cane juice; water substrate fermented for 24 h; F_{24F}: 50% sugar cane juice; 50% added substrate fermented for 24 h; P_{24M}: Fresh palm wine sourced from Mowe analyzed after 24 h; P_{24S}: Fresh palm wine sourced from Sango analyzed after 24 h

Table 4.10: Physiochemical composition of Simulated Palm Wine and Natural Palm Wine after 48 hours fermentation

Parameters	H _{48Z}	S _{48T}	F _{48F}	P _{48M}	P _{48S}	F(p)
Total soluble solids (TSS %)	6.40 ± 0.00a	3.75 ± 0.00b	3.30 ± 0.00c	3.70 ± 0.14b	3.95 ± 0.21b	501.654 (<0.001)
Sucrose %	6.09 ± 0.01a	3.75 ± 0.21b	2.35 ± 0.07c	2.75 ± 0.07a	2.60 ± 0.28d	294.284 (<0.001)
Total sugar (as % invert)	5.40 ± 0.00a	3.55 ± 0.07b	1.30 ± 0.14c	1.26 ± 0.07c	0.30 ± 0.01c	1407.722 (0.001)
Glucose %	1.35 ± 0.03a	0.26 ± 0.00c	0.65 ± 0.07b	1.27 ± 0.08a	1.32 ± 0.13a	72.288 (< 0.001)
Specific gravity (SPG)	1.008 ± 0.01a	1.005 ± 0.00b	1.003 ± 0.00c	1.002 ± 0.00d	1.002 ± 0.00d	72.185 (<0.001)
Ethanol (% vv)	7.20 ± 0.00a	6.35 ± 0.07b	3.16 ± 0.00c	4.05 ± 0.21d	4.47 ± 0.06c	335.271 (<0.001)
pH	4.35 ± 0.07b	4.15 ± 0.07c	4.00 ± 0.00a	3.95 ± 0.04d	3.88 ± 0.01c	72.692 (0.001)
Total Acidity (as Lactic) %	0.40 ± 0.001c	0.47 ± 0.00d	0.49 ± 0.01c	0.73 ± 0.01a	0.66 ± 0.01b	2237.750 (<0.001)
Fat content (%)	0.16 ± 0.01c	0.07 ± 0.00d	0.03 ± 0.01a	0.60 ± 0.01a	0.29 ± 0.02b	691.433 (<0.001)
Protein (%)	0.45 ± 0.01a	0.42 ± 0.03a	0.42 ± 0.01a	0.29 ± 0.01b	0.31 ± 0.01b	41.481 (0.001)
Total ash (%)	0.20 ± 0.01b	0.11 ± 0.01c	0.12 ± 0.01c	0.29 ± 0.01a	0.31 ± 0.00a	172.850 (<0.001)
Sodium (mg/100ml)	4.91 ± 1.39a	7.84 ± 0.04a	3.85 ± 0.07a	21.60 ± 0.28a	12.89 ± 14.86a	2.367 (0.185)
Vitamin C (mg/100ml)	47.30 ± 0.42a	42.25 ± 0.21	38.80 ± 0.14c	8.16 ± 1.34d	8.81 ± 0.08d	1776.797 (<0.001)
Sodium chloride (%)	0.015 ± 0.01b	0.020 ± 0.001b	0.016 ± 0.001b	0.45 ± 0.01a	0.045 ± 0.01a	16.151 (0.005)
Sulphur dioxide (mg/kg)	2.11 ± 0.00a	1.36 ± 0.911	1.02 ± 0.53a	0.32 ± 0.00c	0.29 ± 0.00c	19.781 (0.003)

Sample of means with same alphabet superscripts on a row are not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$)

Legend:

H_{48Z}: 100% sugar cane juice; 0% added water, substrate fermented for 48 h

S_{48T}: 70% sugar cane juice; water substrate fermented for 48 h

F_{48F}: 50% sugar cane juice; 50% added substrate fermented for 48 h

P_{48M}: Natural palm wine sourced from Mowe analyzed after 48 h

P_{48S}: Natural palm wine sourced from Sango analyzed after 48 h

3.5 Effect of Substrate Formulation and Duration of Fermentation on the Sensory Quality of the Simulated Palm Wine.

The result of the sensory evaluation of the simulated palm wine samples in terms of taste, colour, palm wine smell, sweetness and overall acceptability are recorded in table 3.11 – 3.14.

The result of the sensory evaluation of the simulated palm wine samples for taste showed that the low score for taste of samples F₁₂F (5.60) S₁₂T (6.88) and H₁₂Z (8.13) when compared to their corresponding substrate blends fermented for 24 h, F₂₄F (6.16), S₂₄T (7.20) and H₂₄Z (7.84) could be due to the shorter fermentation period of the substrate. This may have resulted from the shorter contact time and the adjustment of the yeast to the high sucrose concentration and fermentation environment at the commencement of fermentation leading to the low alcohol content produced after 12 h fermentation (Table 4.12); F₁₂F (3.31% v/v), S₁₂T (3.31% v/v) and H₁₂Z (3.49% v/v). The high concentration of unfermented sucrose F₁₂F (4.09%) S₁₂T (4.11%) and H₁₂Z (8.80%) may have also combined to influence the low mean score for taste as scored by the panelist for the 12 h fermented simulated palm wine samples (Table 4.12). These may have made the samples to be sweeter tasting than alcoholic in taste.

Generally, with increased rate of fermentation over a 24 h period there was observed increase in alcohol content (Table 3.12) of the samples F₂₄F (3.50% v/v), S₂₄T (7.00% v/v) and H₂₄Z (8.47% v/v) and reduced sucrose content F₂₄F (3.36%), S₂₄T (3.65%) and H₂₄Z (8.03%). This may have influenced the higher mean sensory score for taste for the 24 h fermented samples F₂₄F (6.16), S₂₄T (7.20) and H₂₄Z (7.84) (Table 3.13).

The mean score for taste of the 24 h fermented simulated palm wine samples H₂₄Z (7.84) and S₂₄T (7.20) were not significantly different from the taste of natural palm wine P₂₄M (7.92) and they were the most preferred by the panelist in terms of the taste.

The sensory evaluation results (Table 3.12-3.14) showed that the mean score for colour of the samples increased to creamy white with longer fermentation period, as the panelist score for the 12 h fermented samples were lower than 24 h fermented samples and the 24 h fermented samples were lower than that of 48 h fermented samples. This increase in the creamy white colour of the samples with fermentation was an acceptable development as their colour tended towards the whitish colour of natural palm wine. The white colour of the samples which improved with fermentation duration may be attributed to the growth of more yeast and accumulation of yeast biomass. This is consistent with the report of Legras *et al.*, (2017) that yeast is morphologically white in colour and their heavy suspension in the palm wine gave a milky white appearance and contribute to the whitish turbidity of palm wine. According to Okeke and Obi (2021) the accumulation of yeast biomass may create a more whitish colour and this improves with fermentation. Adamu-Governor *et al.*, (2018) reported that within 12 to 24 h, yeast utilized the sugar in the substrate to simultaneously grow in large biomass, and the production of gums from glucans and fructans during the fermentation of the sugars in palm sap substrates, resulted in the development of the creamy white colour of natural palm wine. These colour changes may have contributed the high mean score for the colour of simulated palm wine samples which were

comparable to the colour of natural palm wine, particularly samples H_{24Z} (7.20) and S_{24T} (7.20) which have mean scores comparable to that of natural palm wine (7.88) P_{24M}.

The sensory score obtained for the smell (palm wine smell), showed that there was a progressive increase in palm wine smell with longer fermentation period. This may have arisen due to the fermentation of the sugar in the substrate to alcohol and acid and the associated reaction of the produced alcohol with the acid to produce esters. The strength of this smell according to Bitrus *et al.*, 2020 and Laseken *et al.*, (2013) depends on the duration of fermentation period, the kind of esters formed and their quantity.

Therefore, the lower mean scores for smell recorded for the 12 h fermented simulated palm wine samples F_{12F} (6.28), S_{12T} (7.00) and H_{12Z} (6.20) may be due to the lower development of alcohol and their esters within 12 h fermentation. Noticeably too, the mean score for smell of samples fermented for 24 h. were higher than that of 12 h fermented samples F_{24F} (6.32), S_{24T} (6.80) and H_{24Z} (7.48) and these were higher than the 48 h fermented samples F_{48F} (6.73), S_{48T} (6.56) and H_{48Z} (6.88).

The lower mean score obtained for 48 h fermented simulated palm wine samples may have arisen due to oxidation of alcohols due to longer fermentation period hence lower yield of esters and continued increase on acidity with time, leading to the development of more acidic smell and according to Joshi *et al.*, (2017), if palm wine is allowed to ferment longer than 24 h it starts develops vinigery smell.

As the sugar content was depleted and alcohol was produced the less sweet the samples become with longer fermentation period. This may be responsible for the lower score for sweetness for samples fermented for 24 h and 48 h respectively. F_{24F} (6.04), S_{24T} (5.88) and H_{24Z} (5.96) and F_{48F} (6.04), S_{48T} (5.88) and H_{48Z} (5.96) when compared to samples fermented for 12 h F_{12F} (6.88), S_{12T} (7.64) and H_{12Z} (7.80). The observed decrease in sucrose concentration with increasing fermentation duration could be attributed to the fermentation of the sugar contained in the substrate which resulted from the conversion of sugar to alcohol thereby reducing the sweetness of the fermented samples.

The mean sensory score for sweetness of the samples may have been influenced by the reduction in the concentration of sucrose in the samples as shown in tables 4.8 where sucrose content decreased from the samples fermented for 12 h H_{12Z} (8.80%), S_{12T} (4.11%) and F_{12F} (4.09%) to H_{24Z} (8.03%), S_{24T} (3.65%) and F_{24F} (3.36%) and further decreased with 48 h fermentation H_{48Z} (6.09%), S_{48T} (3.75%) and samples F_{48F}(2.35%) with fermentation is consistent with the report of Djeni *et al.*, (2020) that the sugar in palm sap was utilized over a period of 24 h fermentation, making the palm sap lose its sweetness. This observed trend conformed with the finding of Adekaren *et al.*, (2017) that palm sap is very sweet and non-alcoholic tasting as it is been tapped from palm tree and becomes less sweet and alcoholic within 24 h.

Result showed that the overall acceptability scores for the 24 h fermented simulated palm wine samples S_{24T} (7.48) and H_{24Z} (7.88) were comparable to the mean score for the natural palm wine P_{24M} (7.88). This showed that the simulated palm wine samples (H_{24Z} and S_{24T}) were the

most preferred and acceptable. Their sensory characteristics compared very closely with that of natural palm wine P₂₄M (7.88). This assertion is consistent with results of the sensory evaluation scores for sample H₂₄Z colour (7.20), taste (7.84), and smell (7.48) and sweetness (7.24) and also for sample S₂₄T for colour (7.8), taste (7.20), smell (6.80) and sweetness (7.24).

These values compared closely with the sensory evaluation scores obtained for natural palm wine sample fermented for 24 h P₂₄M, for colour (7.88), taste (7.92) smell (7.88) and sweetness (7.92). These results showed the consistent resemblance between the panelist preference for taste, colour, smell, sweetness and overall acceptability of the simulated palm wine samples with that of natural palm wine samples. Indicatively, simulated palm wine samples H₂₄Z and S₂₄T were the most preferred and their sensory characteristics compared very closely with that of natural palm wine.

Table 3.11: Sensory evaluation scores of simulated palm wine after 12 hrs fermentation

Samples	Taste	Colour	Smell	Sweetness	Overall Acceptability
F ₁₂ F	5.60 ± 1.73 ^c	6.60 ± 1.63 ^b	6.28 ± 1.65 ^b	6.88 ± 1.48 ^b	6.08 ± 1.47 ^c
S ₁₂ T	6.88 ± 1.83 ^b	7.40 ± 1.12 ^a	6.40 ± 1.66 ^b	7.64 ± 1.50 ^a	7.12 ± 1.49 ^b
H ₁₂ Z	7.24 ± 1.71 ^{ab}	5.96 ± 2.03 ^b	6.20 ± 1.87 ^a	7.80 ± 1.78 ^a	7.20 ± 1.78 ^{ab}
P ₁₂ M	8.13 ± 0.74 ^a	7.96 ± 0.75 ^a	7.92 ± 0.75 ^a	7.92 ± 0.78 ^a	8.25 ± 0.61 ^a
F-statistics (p)	10.866 (<0.001)	9.541 (<0.001)	6.329 (<0.001)	11.082 (<0.001)	

Means with same alphabet superscripts on a column are not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$)

Legend

F₁₂F: 50 % sugar cane juice: blended with 50% added water substrate fermented for 12 h

S₁₂T: 70 % sugar cane juice blended with 30% added water; substrate fermented for 12 h

H₁₂Z: 100 % sugar cane juice blended with 0% added water; substrate fermented for 12 h

P₁₂M: Fresh palm wine sourced from Mowe, analyzed after 12 h

Table 3.12: Sensory evaluation scores of simulated palm wine after 24 hours fermentation

Samples	Taste	Colour	Smell	Sweetness	Overall Acceptability
F ₂₄ F	6.16 ± 2.17 ^b	6.90 ± 1.76 ^b	6.42 ± 1.25 ^c	6.12 ± 1.94 ^b	6.32 ± 1.68 ^b
S ₂₄ T	7.20 ± 1.55 ^a	7.60 ± 1.19 ^a	6.50 ± 1.68 ^b	7.24 ± 1.54 ^a	7.48 ± 1.48 ^b
H ₂₄ Z	7.84 ± 1.31 ^a	7.30 ± 1.29 ^a	6.88 ± 0.92 ^{ab}	7.60 ± 1.35 ^a	7.88 ± 1.27 ^a
P ₂₄ M	7.92 ± 0.65 ^a	7.88 ± 0.68 ^a	7.88 ± 0.74 ^a	7.92 ± 0.78 ^a	7.88 ± 0.85 ^a
F-statistics(p)	6.984 (<0.001)	5.574 (<0.001)	8.122 (<0.001)	7.744 (<0.001)	7.325 (<.001)

Means with same alphabet superscripts on a column are not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$)

Legend:

F₂₄F: 50 % sugar cane juice: blended with 50 % added water, substrate fermented for 24 h

S₂₄T: 70 % sugar cane juice blended with 30 % added water, substrate fermented for 24 h

H₂₄Z: 100 % sugar cane juice blended with 0% added water, substrate fermented for 24 h

P₂₄M: Fresh palm wine sourced from Mowe, analyzed after 24 h

Table 3.13: Sensory evaluation scores of simulated palm wine after 48 hrs fermentation

Samples	Taste	Colour	Smell	Sweetness	Overall Acceptability
F ₄₈ F	5.38 ± 1.47 ^b	6.96 ± 1.66 ^{ab}	6.73 ± 1.48 ^a	6.04 ± 1.51 ^b	6.27 ± 1.48 ^a
S ₄₈ T	5.84 ± 2.10 ^b	7.16 ± 1.43 ^a	6.56 ± 1.80 ^a	5.88 ± 2.37 ^b	6.28 ± 2.19 ^a
H ₄₈ Z	6.16 ± 1.68 ^b	7.82 ± 1.46 ^b	6.68 ± 1.62 ^a	5.96 ± 1.84 ^b	6.48 ± 1.76 ^a
P ₄₈ M	7.30 ± 0.76 ^a	7.48 ± 0.73 ^a	7.48 ± 0.90 ^a	7.57 ± 0.79 ^a	7.52 ± 0.67 ^a
F-statistics(p)	3.711 (0.014)	3.037 (0.033)	1.680 (0.060)	5.036 (0.001)	2.628 (0.055)

Sample of means with same alphabet superscripts on a column are not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$)

Legend:

F₄₈F: 50 % sugar cane juice: blended with 50% added water, substrate fermented for 48 h

S₄₈T: 70 % sugar cane juice blended with 30% added water, substrate fermented for 48 h

H₄₈Z: 100 % sugar cane juice blended with 0% added water, substrate fermented for 48 h

P₄₈M: Fresh palm wine sourced from Mowe, analyzed after 48 h

4.0 Conclusion

The locally - fabricated fermenter could be used to produce an acceptable simulated palm wine with characteristics comparable to that of natural palm wine.

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